

Additions to the Lepidoptera fauna of Omsk and Novosibirsk Regions, Russia

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Abstract

The article provides a list of 23 species from the Chimabachidae, Pieridae, Nymphalidae, Geometridae, Notodontidae, Erebidae, Noctuidae families from Omsk and Novosibirsk Regions in West Siberia. Three species – *Pseudobaptria corydalaria* (Graeser, 1889), *Paragona cognata* (Staudinger, 1892), *Polia malchani* (Draudt, 1934) are new to the South-West Siberian Region in Catalogue of Lepidoptera of Russia. Three species are new to the Omsk Region, among them *Pseudobaptria corydalaria* (Graeser, 1889), *Scopula incanata* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Egira conspicillaris* (Linnaeus, 1758); seven species are new to Novosibirsk Region, among them *Dasystema salicella* (Hübner, 1796), *Apatura ilia* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775), *Stauropus fagi* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Catocala deducta* Eversmann, 1843, *Acronicta menyanthidis* (Esper, 1789), *Amphipyra pyramidea* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Euxoa nigrofusca* (Esper, [1788]).

Keywords

Lepidoptera, Chimabachidae, Pieridae, Nymphalidae, Geometridae, Notodontidae, Erebidae, Arctiinae, Lymantriinae, Boletobiinae, Noctuidae, West Siberia, Omsk Region, Novosibirsk Region, fauna, new records

Introduction

The entomofauna of the South of the West Siberian Plain has been studied well last two decades (Knyazev 2009; Knyazev 2020; Knyazev et Ponomarev 2020; Knyazev

et Mironov 2021; Knyazev et al. 2021; Knyazev 2022; Knyazev et al. 2022; Knyazev et Sinev 2023; Knyazev et al. 2024a; Knyazev et al. 2024b; Knyazev et Ivonin 2025a, 2025b; Knyazev 2025). However, despite careful studies of the Lepidoptera fauna, it is still possible to find species new to the regions. The northernmost and southernmost territories are particularly interesting in this aspect, which are often difficult to access and therefore have been ignored by entomologists for a long time. In 2025, we undertook several expeditions to such areas of the Omsk and Novosibirsk regions, where we collected materials that served as the basis for this publication.

Materials and methods

All material processed within the framework of this article was collected on the territories of Omsk and Novosibirsk Regions by the authors using standard method of collecting by butterfly net and by attracting at light of the Mercury lamps. All collected specimens are deposited in the collections of Svyatoslav Knyazev (CSKO, Omsk, Russia) and Vadim Ivonin (CVIN, Novosibirsk, Russia). The identification of the material was carried out using modern keys and taxonomic revisions. All photos were made using a Canon EOS 5D Mark II camera with a Canon EF-100mm macro lens, Canon PowerShot G7 and Xiaomi Redmi Note 10Pro smartphone camera.

List of the collecting sites:

Omsk Region:

Baronovka – Sedel'nikovskiy district, Baronovka boundary, Mainsas river bank, 56.843637, 75.322818;

Bol'shaya Tebendya – Ust'-Ishim district, 5 km NW of Bol'shaya Tebendya village, 57.718605, 70.753975;

Buzan – Russko-Polyanskyy district, 2 km SE of Buzan village, 53.911713, 73.948744;

Chernoluchye – Omsk district, Chernoluchye village, 55.293109, 73.037241;

Firstovo – Bol'sheukovskiy district, Firstovo village vicinity, 57.0340633321, 72.9010039836;

Elita – Omskiy district, Omsk City, Elita gardens community, 55.027305, 73.550731;

Muromtsevo – Muromtsevskiy district, Muromtsevo village vicinity, Tara river bank, 56.379416, 75.270567;

Pavlovka – Sedel'nikovskiy district, 1 km SW of Pavlovka village, Isass river bank, 56.786033, 75.128794;

Ryazany (Fig. 1) – Muromtsevskiy district, 4 km SW of Ryazany village, 56.538791, 75.184302;

Sedel'nikovo (Fig. 2) – Sedel'nikovskiy district, Sedel'nikovo village vicinity, 56.936829, 75.333804;

Tara – Tarskiy district, Tara town vicinity, 56.911378, 74.328603;

Tleusai (Fig. 3) – Russko-Polyansky district, 8 km SW of Khlebodarovka village, river Tleusai, 53.714771, 73.359083;

Victory Park – Omsk City, Victory Park, 54.9675651433, 73.3667270467;

Yakovlevka (Fig. 4) – Bol'sheukovskiy district, 28 km NW of Bolshiye Uki village, Yakovlevka boundary, river Tevri, 57.177442, 72.421206;

Novosibirsk Region:

Bezmyanny Ryam – Chulymsky district, 10 km N of Kabinetnoye rail station, 1 km SE of Kuznetsky village, 55.164614, 81.319200;

Demidov Ryam – Ust'-Tarskiy district, 4,5 km NW of Yarkul' Matyushkino, 55.876808, 76.019997;

Duplenskaya – Kochenevskiy district, 8,5 km E of Duplenskaya village, 2,5 km S of Aleksandrovskiy village, 55.099757, 81.759210;

Gus'kovskiy Ryam (Fig. 5) – Chulymsky district, 18 km N of Kabinetnoye rail station, 3 km N of Kuznetsky village, 55.204647, 81.293100;

Karasuk – Karasuk district, Karasuk town suburbs, 53.717133, 78.110322;

Khorosheye – Karasuk district, Khorosheye village vicinity, 53.603814, 78.439631;

Kyshtovka – Kyshtovskiy district, 6,5 km W of Kyshtovka village, near Karbalyk lake, 56.576564, 76.512081;

Lineva (Fig. 6) – Kyshtovskiy district, 9 km SW of Malokrasnoyarka village, Lineva lake, 56.429872, 75.872058;

Malokrasnoyarka – Kyshtovskiy district, Malokrasnoyarka village vicinity, 56.470556, 76.008333;

Novosibirsk, Vystavochnaya – Novosibirsk City, Vystavochnaya street, 54.989848, 82.895780;

Oktyabrskoye – Karasukskiy district, 1 km South of Oktyabrskoye village, 53.470200, 77.810664;

Orlovka (Fig. 7) – Kyshtovskiy district, Orlovka village vicinity, River Ui bank, 56.948661, 76.335611;

Salair – Toguchinskiy district, 2,5 km SE of Koltyrak village, border of the Novosibirsk and Kemerovo Regions, Salair mountain ridge, valley of the Istok River, 54.778000, 84.949528;

Shelkovichikha – Novosibirsk district, N of Shelkovitshikha rail station, right bank of the river Inya, forest near the Berezka gardens community, 55.009167, 83.333483;

Solyonoye – Karasukskiy district, Lake Solenoye, east of the village Khorosheye, 53.566628, 78.602447;

Zaeltsovskiy bor – Novosibirskiy district, 4 km SW of cemetery, 55.044573, 82.513830;

Zayachya Gora – the border of Novosibirsk and Kemerovo Regions, SE bank of Tanaev pond, 3 km SW of Zhuravlevo in Kemerovo Region, 54.761078, 85.018328.

Figure 1. Habitats: Omsk Region, Ryazany, 27.04.2025, photo by S.A. Knyazev.

Figure 2. Habitats: Omsk Region, Sedel'nikovo, 28.04.2025, photo by S.A. Knyazev.

Figure 3. Habitats: Omsk Region, Tleusai, 26.09.2025, photo by S.A. Knyazev.

Figure 4. Habitats: Omsk Region, Yakovlevka, 20.06.2025, photo by S.A. Knyazev.

Figure 5. Habitats: Novosibirsk Region, Gus`kovsky Ryam, 11.05.2012, photo by V.V. Ivonin.

Figure 6. Habitats: Novosibirsk Region, Lineva, 1.06.2025, photo by V.V. Ivonin.

Figure 7. Habitats: Novosibirsk Region, Orlovka, 2.06.2025, photo by V.V. Ivonin.

Results

Chimabachidae

Dasystoma salicella (Hübner, 1796)

Figs 8, 24

Material examined. Omsk Region: 13♂♂, Muromtsevo, 27.04.2025, S.A. Knyazev (CSKO); 7♂♂, Ryazany, 27.04.2025, S.A. Knyazev (CSKO); 2♂♂, Pavlovka, 28.04.2025, S.A. Knyazev (CSKO); 2♂♂, Baronovka, 28.04.2025, S.A. Knyazev (CSKO); 7♂♂, Sedel'nikovo, 28.04.2025, S.A. Knyazev (CSKO); 1♂, Elita, 12.04.2025, S.M. Saikina (CSKO); **Novosibirsk Region:** 2♂♂, Duplenskaya, 16.04.2025, S.A. Knyazev (CSKO).

Remark. New to Novosibirsk Region. Widespread Transpalaeartic species distributed in Russia from European Part to Far East. In West Siberia it is known from two localities in Omsk Region (Knyazev 2022) and from Altai Republic (Knyazev et Ivonin 2025b). Early spring species which was collected in 2025 in several localities using synthetic pheromones by Pherobank.

Pieridae

Colias erate (Esper, 1803)

Material examined. Omsk Region: 1♂, Tleusai, 26.09.2025, S.A. Knyazev (CSKO).

Remark. The second record in the Omsk Region 18 years after the first meeting (Knyazev 2009). Rare and local species in West Siberia. The specimen was found together with the common and widespread species *Colias hyale* (Linnaeus, 1758).

Nymphalidae

Apatura ilia ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)

Figs 9, 27

Material examined. Omsk Region: 6♂, Yakovlevka, 20.06.2025, S.A. Knyazev (CSKO); mass gathering of butterflies on a muddy road, Yakovlevka, 26.06.2025, V.Yu. Teploukhov (<https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/293681758>); 1♂, Bol'shiye Uki, 20.06.2025, S.A. Knyazev (<https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/291529417>); 1♂, Firstovo, 24.06.2025, V.Yu. Teploukhov (<https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/292391459>); 1♂, Tara, 21.06.2025, S.A. Knyazev (visual registration); 1♂, Omsk City, 17.06.2025 (<https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/291352507>); 1♂, Omsk City, 28.06.2025, A.A. Poteiko (<https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/293309356>); 1♀, Buzan, 11.07.2025, K.B. Ponomarev (photo); **Novosibirsk Region:** 2♂, Malokrasnoyarka, 26.06.2025, V.V. Ivonin (CVIN); 3♂, Kyshtovka, 26.06.2025, V.V. Ivonin (CVIN); 2♂, Orlovka, 26.06.2025, V.V. Ivonin (CVIN).

Remark. New to Novosibirsk Region. This nemoral species has recently begun to populate Western Siberia. In 2020, it was recorded in the Tyumen region, in 2023 it was found in the Omsk region (Knyazev et al. 2024), where it has become numerous in recent years and it has already settled south down to the forest-steppe and steppe zones (finds in Omsk and Buzan). At the end of June 2025, a few males were observed on gravel roads between villages in the northwestern part of the Novosibirsk region. The butterflies kept to roadside wetlands, small streams, with *Salix*, *Betula*, *Populus tremula*.

Limnitis camilla (Linnaeus, 1764)

Fig. 26

Material examined. Omsk Region: 9 specimens, Yakovlevka, 20.06.2025, S.A. Knyazev (CSKO); 1 specimen, Firstovo, 24.06.2025, V.Yu. Teploukhov (<https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/292391205>).

Remark. An Amphipalaeartic species distributed in Russia in European Part, Urals, Western Siberia and after large gap in the Far East (Sinev 2019). The species

has recently begun to settle in Western Siberia, moving from West to East together with *Apatura ilia* (Knyazev et al. 2024). New findings in the Omsk region confirm the advance of the species from West to East, which may mean the imminent appearance of the species in the Novosibirsk region in nearest years.

Satyrinae

Pseudochazara hippolyte (Esper, 1784)

Material examined. Omsk Region: 1♀, Yakovlevka, 20.06.2025, S.A. Knyazev (CSKO).

Remark. This steppe xerophilous species distributed in the southern regions of the Omsk region (Knyazev 2020). The new find was made above 400 km to the North of the main range of the species, which can be regarded either as an accidental flight due to strong winds, or an attempt by the female to settle in search of suitable stations in order to expand the range. However, the northern swampy forests of the subtaiga zone could hardly be suitable for establishing a new population of the species in this place. This is the northernmost find of the species.

Geometridae

Epirranthis diversata ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)

Fig. 28

Material examined. Omsk Region: 4♂♂, 2♀, Sedel'nikovo, 28.04.2025, S.A. Knyazev (CSKO); 35♂♂, 4♀ Ryazany, 27.04.2025, S.A. Knyazev (CSKO).

Remark. It is a widespread Transpalaeartic but infrequent early spring species, previously known in the Omsk region from few localities (Knyazev 2020; Knyazev et al. 2022). In general, a species with a low population in 2025 gave the outbreak of mass reproduction and were found in large numbers in the north-east of the region. Caterpillars foodplants are *Populus* and *Salix species* (Beljaev 2016).

Macaria brunneata (Thunberg, 1784)

Material examined. Novosibirsk Region: 2♀, Zael'tsovsky Bor, 3.07.1982, V.V. Ivonin (CVIN); 1♂, Bezymyanny Ryam, 14.07.2013, V.V. Ivonin (CVIN); 2♂, Karasuk, 12-13.07.2024, V.V. Ivonin (CVIN); 2♂, Solyonoye, 11-12.07.2024 V.V. Ivonin (CVIN).

Remark. Widespread transpalaeartic species. In the Novosibirsk region, this species is typical for northern coniferous forests and sphagnum swamps (Vasilenko 2006). New records in the southwest of the region look unusual. Caterpillars found on *Vaccinium*, *Ledum* (Beljaev 2016).

***Acasis appensata* (Eversmann, 1842)**

Fig. 10

Material examined. Novosibirsk Region: 1♂, Lineva, 1-2.06.2025, V.V. Ivonin (CVIN).

Remark. Transpalaeartic forest species. In Novosibirsk Region it was previously known from Novosibirsky, Ubinsky, and the border of Maslyaninsky and Toghuchinsky districts (Vasilenko et Ivonin 2020; Ivonin et al 2021). The new record is the first from the northwest of the Novosibirsk Region. Caterpillars found on *Actaea*, *Valeriana*, *Veronica* (Beljaev 2016).

***Asthena albulata* (Hufnagel, 1767)**

Fig. 11

Material examined. Omsk Region: 1♂, Sedel'nikovo, 20-21.08.2025, S.A. Knyazev (CSKO).

Remark. Euro-Siberian species, rare and local in West Siberia. It was found in Omsk Region only once, in the Sedelnikovskiy district, near the village Yelnichnoye in 2014 (Knyazev et al. 2015). A new discovery in late August suggests the possibility of a second generation of this species in Western Siberia. The caterpillars foodplants are *Carpinus*, *Corylus*, *Fagus*, *Betula*, *Quercus*, *Tilia*, *Populus*, *Rosa* (Hausmann et Viidalepp 2012).

***Pseudobaptria corydalaria* (Graeser, 1889)**

Figs 12, 29

Material examined. Omsk Region: 3♂♂, Yakovlevka, 20.06.2025, S.A. Knyazev (CSKO).

Remark. The first record of the species in the South-West Siberian region and in Omsk Region. Previously this species was known in Russia from the Khanty-Mansi Autonomous Okrug, the Baikal Region, the Nizhny Amur Region and the Primorye Territory; outside Russia the species distributed in Japan, Korea and China (Sinev 2019; Beljaev 2016). According to literature data, the caterpillars of this species develop on *Corydalis* species (Beljaev 2016). Probably, the food plant of the caterpillars of this species in the Omsk region may be *Corydalis capnoides* (L.) Pers., the only one *Corydalis* species known in the region.

***Scopula incanata* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Fig. 13

Material examined. Omsk Region: 3♂♂, Bol'shaya Tebendya, at light, 10-11.06.2023, S.A. Knyazev, S.M. Saikina (CSKO, ZISP).

Remark. New to Omsk Region. It is a widespread species in Russia, found from the European part to southern Yakutia (Sinev 2019). Caterpillars are polyphagous, found on different plants such as *Polygonum*, *Sorbus*, *Thymus*, *Origanum*, *Teucrium*, *Campanula*, *Lychnis*, *Dianthus*, *Hippocrepis*, *Cytisus*, *Clematis*, *Campanula*, *Lonicera*, *Rhamnus*, *Taraxacum* (Hausmann 2004).

Notodontidae

Stauropus fagi (Linnaeus, 1758)

Figs 14, 25

Material examined. Omsk Region: 1♂, Bol'sheukovsky district, Bol'shiye Uki village, 7.05.2025, V.Yu. Teploukhov (<https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/281715831>); **Novosibirsk Region:** 1♂, Lineva, 1-2.06.2025, V.V. Ivonin (CVIN).

Remark. New to Novosibirsk Region. In 2013, it was given for the first time for the territory of Western Siberia from the Omsk region (Knyazev et al. 2013). After that, it was found there in many locations (Knyazev 2020). In addition, the species was reported from Altai Republic (Knyazev 2023), and also from the Altai Territory and the Kemerovo region (Efimov et al. 2024). In the Novosibirsk region it is not often found in mixed forests, inhabits the northwestern part of the region. Caterpillars foodplants are *Quercus*, *Fagus*, *Malus*, *Salix*, *Populus*, *Tilia*, *Acer*, *Zelkovia*, *Carpinus*, *Pterocarya*, *Castanea*, *Corylus*, *Betula*, *Wisteria*, *Prunus*, *Cornus*, *Crataegus* (Schintlmeister, 2008).

Erebidae

Lymantriinae

Calliteara pudibunda (Linnaeus, 1758)

Fig. 15

Material examined. Omsk Region: 1♂, Bol'sheukovsky district, Bol'shiye Uki village, 7.05.2025, V.Yu. Teploukhov (<https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/279171514>); **Novosibirsk Region:** 3♂♂, Orlovka, 3-4.06.2025, V.V. Ivonin (CVIN); 4♂♂1♀, Lineva, 1-2.06.2025, V.V. Ivonin (CVIN); 17♂♂, Kyshtovka, 31.05-1.06.2025, V.V. Ivonin (CVIN)

Remark. A nemoral species with a disjunctive range found in the European part of Russia, in the Urals, in Zabaikalye territory and further in the Far East (Sinev 2019). In Western Siberia it is known from the Omsk region (Knyazev 2020) where it is common and abundant. There is only one indication of the presence of the species in the Novosibirsk region from Akademgorodok (Kolomiets 1981), possibly erroneous, since over the years the species has not been found in this location. It

is common in the north-west of the region in mixed and birch forests. Caterpillars found on different wood plants: *Quercus*, *Betula*, *Carpinus*, *Corylus*, *Malus*, *Pyrus*, *Prunus* (Tshistyakov et al. 2016).

Figures 8–15. Adult specimens of Lepidoptera: **8** – *Dasytoma salicella*, Duplenskaya (CSKO); **9** – *Apatura ilia*, Kyshtovka (CVIN); **10** – *Acasis appensata*, Lineva (CVIN); **11** – *Asthena albulata*, Sedel'nikovo (CSKO); **12** – *Pseudobaptria corydalaria*, Yakovlevka (CSKO); **13** – *Scopula incanata*, Bol'shaya Tebendya (CSKO); **14** – *Stauropus fagi*, Lineva (CVIN); **15** – *Calliteara pudibunda*, Kyshtovka (CVIN).

Arctiinae

Diacrisia metelkana (Lederer, 1861)

Fig. 16

Material examined. Novosibirsk Region: 4♂, Chebachye, 12-13.06.2025 and 28-29.06.2025, V.V. Ivonin (CVIN).

Remark. Hygrophilous rare and local species distributed in Russia in the Volga basin, Dagestan, southern Western Siberia (Omsk and Novosibirsk Regions), in the Far East (Sinev 2019; Knyazev 2020). In the Novosibirsk region, it is known from one point in Krotovaya Lyaga (Dubatolov et Zolotarenko 1990). The caterpillars are polyphagous, live on the *Phragmites* from where they move to other aquatic plants, such as *Iris*, *Nymphaea alba* (where they eat round holes in the middle of the leaves), as well as *Euphorbia*, *Taraxacum*, *Caltha*, and *Polygonum persicaria* (Murzin, 2003).

Boletobiinae

Paragona cognata (Staudinger, 1892)

Fig. 17

Material examined. Novosibirsk Region: 1♂, Oktyabrskoye, 27.06.2024, V.V. Ivonin (CVIN); 1♂, Khorosheye, 9.07.2024, V.V. Ivonin (CVIN); 1♂, Karasuk, 29-30.06.2025, V.V. Ivonin (CVIN).

Remark. New to the South-West Siberian Region. The general distribution of the species in Russia covers the mountainous regions of Siberia up to the Far East (Sinev 2019). It was previously known in the Novosibirsk region from Akademgorodok and from Salair (Dubatolov 2013, Ivonin et al. 2021). In the southwest of the Region it is not numerous. Preimaginal stages and foodplants are unknown.

Erebinae

Catocala deducta Eversmann, 1843

Fig. 18

Material examined. Novosibirsk Region: 1♀, Khorosheye, 28.08.2025, V.V. Ivonin (CVIN).

Remark. New to Novosibirsk Region. The species was reported from Gorno-Altai as *C. elocata* (Esper, 1786) according to the materials from 1960 (Zolotarenko et Bubnova 1978). In another work (Zolotarenko et Tumaikina 1978), additional sites were reported in the village of Klyuchi and Barnaul (Altai Territory). It was noted that the species has not yet been found north of Novosibirsk. There are no materials from the Novosibirsk region in the collection of ISEA. There is one more recent find of this species (as *C. elocata*) from the Altai Territory (Davydov et al.

2023). The foodplants of the caterpillars are known for the closely related species *C. elocata*: *Alnus*, *Populus*, *Salix* spp. (Matov et Kononenko 2012).

Noctuidae

Acronicta menyanthidis (Esper, 1789)

Fig. 19

Material examined. Novosibirsk Region: 1♀, Demidov Ryam, 25-26.06.2017, V.V. Ivonin (CVIN); 1♂, Gus'kovsky Ryam, 25.08.2015, V.V. Ivonin (CVIN); 3♂♂, Bezmyanny Ryam, 23.06.2013 and 13.06.2014, V.V. Ivonin (CVIN).

Remark. New to Novosibirsk Region. It is widespread in the European part of Russia, in the Urals, further through Siberia to the Far East (Kononenko 2010, Sinev 2019). It was recently found in the northern and western regions of the Omsk region (Knyazev et al. 2019; Knyazev 2020). In Novosibirsk region, it inhabits the northern regions and is found in the sphagnum swamps. Caterpillars feed on various herbaceous, woody, and shrubby plants, including *Aconitum*, *Ranunculus*, *Betula*, *Myrica*, *Calluna*, *Erica*, *Oxycoccus*, *Vaccinium*, *Lysimachia*, *Salix*, *Comarum*, *Crataegus*, *Malus*, *Potentilla*, *Rubus*, *Sorbus*, *Cytisus*, *Lythrum*, *Menyanthes*, *Tussilago*, *Juncus*, *Scheuchzeria*, *Poaceae* (Matov et Kononenko 2012).

Simyra dentinosa (Freyer, 1838)

Fig. 31

Material examined. Omsk Region: 1♀, Chernoluchye, 26-27.04.2025, S.A. Knyazev (CSKO); 1♂, Elita, 1-2.05.2025, S.A. Knyazev, S.M. Saikina (CSKO).

Remark. A steppe species inhabiting arid biotopes in the southern part of the Omsk region (Knyazev 2020). The species is also found in the south of the European part of Russia, in the southern Urals and Altai (Sinev 2019). The new findings extend the known range of the species to the north by 170 km and become the northernmost for its range. The larval foodplants are *Euphorbia*, *Centaurea* (Matov et Kononenko 2012).

Amphipyra pyramidea (Linnaeus, 1758)

Fig. 20

Material examined. Omsk Region: 1 spm., Victory Park, 21.07.2025, S.A. Knyazev (<https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/299898477>); **Novosibirsk Region:** 1♂, Novosibirsk City, Vystavochnaya str., 12-13.08.2025, V.V. Ivonin (CVIN).

Remark. It is a widespread species found in Russia from the European part to Western Siberia, and then, after a large gap, in the Far East. In Western Siberia it is known from the Tyumen and Omsk regions (Zolotarenko et Dubatolov 2000; Knyazev et al. 2010; Knyazev 2020). In the Novosibirsk region, it was recorded

within the city. In September 2002, moths were observed in quite large numbers in 2.5 km from the railway station Shelkovichikha, the right bank of the Inya River in the Berezka gardens community (observation by V.V. Ivonin). Caterpillars are polyphagous, found on different plants from the families Fagaceae, Betulaceae, Juglandaceae, Actinidiaceae, Ericaceae, Salicaceae, Tiliaceae, Ulmaceae, Grossulariaceae, Rosaceae, Onagraceae, Aceraceae, Hippocastanaceae, Celastraceae, Rhamnaceae, Vitaceae, Hydrangeaceae, Cornaceae, Caprifoliaceae, Viburnaceae, Sambucaceae, Oleaceae (Matov et Kononenko 2012).

***Egira conspicillaris* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Figs 21, 30

Material examined. Omsk Region: 1♂, 1♀, Elita, at light, 1-2.05.2025, S.A. Knyazev, S.M. Saikina (CSKO).

Remark. New to Omsk Region. The species was previously reported from Kurgan Region in West Siberia (Zolotarenko et Dubatolov 2000). On the territory of Russia this species is widely distributed from European Part to Southern Urals and South-West Siberian Region (Sinev 2019). In the Omsk region the specimens were collected in meadow-steppe areas of the northern bank of the river Om` is located on the eastern outskirts of Omsk City, in the garden plots. Caterpillars are polyphagous, found on different plants such as *Clematis*, *Polygonum*, *Rumex*, *Quercus*, *Betula*, *Arbutus*, *Salix*, *Tilia*, *Ulmus*, *Prunus*, *Rubus*, *Citrusus*, *Genista*, *Lotus*, *Trifolium*, *Euonymus*, *Fraxinus*, *Phillyrea*, *Plantago*, *Lamium*, *Taraxacum*, different Poaceae (Matov et Kononenko 2012).

***Polia malchani* (Draudt, 1934)**

Fig. 22

Material examined. Novosibirsk Region: 2♂, Orlovka, 2-3.06.2025, V.V. Ivonin (CVIN); 1♂, Salair, 21.05.2020, V.V. Ivonin (CVIN); 3♂, Zayachya Gora, 28.05.2020, V.V. Ivonin (CVIN).

Remark. New to the South-West Siberian Region. Siberian boreomontane species distributed in Russia in mountainous regions from Southern Urals to Far East (Sinev 2019). Previously one male was known from the eastern part of the Novosibirsk region, Zayachya Gora in Salair Range (Knyazev et Ivonin 2011). In 2020, 3 more males were collected at same locality and nearby in the Salairsky Reserve. New findings in the north-western part of the region expand the understanding of the distribution of this species in West Siberia. This species is typical for mountainous regions but rare and local in the West Siberian plain. The caterpillars develop on the *Larix sibirica* (Matov et Kononenko 2012).

***Lacanobia splendens* (Hübner, 1808)**

Material examined. Novosibirsk Region: 1♂, Karasuk, 29–30.06.2025, V.V. Ivonin (CVIN).

Remark. It is a widespread Transpalaeartic species (Sinev 2019). On the West Siberian Plain known from the Omsk Region (Knyazev 2020), Novosibirsk Region and the Altai Territory (Zolotarenko et Dubatolov 2000). The indication for the Novosibirsk region was without mentioning the material, so we confirm the presence of the species and clarify its range in the region. The species is rarely found in steppe biotopes in the southwest of the region. Caterpillars are polyphagous on *Nephrodium*, *Lastrea*, *Thelypteris*, *Aquilegia*, *Atriplex*, *Beta*, *Rumex*, *Lysimachia*, *Trifolium*, *Cicuta*, *Menyanthes*, *Solanum*, *Calystegia*, *Convolvulus*, *Plantago*, *Arctium*, *Artemisia*, *Hieracium*, *Lactuca*, *Prenanthes*, *Sonchus*, *Taraxacum*, *Poaceae* (Matov et Kononenko 2012).

***Euxoa nigrofusca* (Esper, [1788])**

Fig. 23

Material examined. Novosibirsk Region: 2♂♂, Shelkovitchikha, 27.07.2009 and 28.07.2022, V.V. Ivonin (CVIN).

Remark. New to Novosibirsk Region. It is a widespread Transpalaeartic species (Sinev 2019). It was discovered in Western Siberia by the materials from the Omsk region (Knyazev et al. 2013) and found there later in various localities (Knyazev 2020). In the Novosibirsk region, it rather has a wider distribution, but due to the difficulty in determining, it is often confused with other species of the genus *Euxoa*. The specimens were collected in the eastern part of the forest steppe near the pine forest. The caterpillars are polyphagous on different plants such as *Paeonia*, *Cerastium*, *Spergula*, *Stellaria*, *Beta*, *Chenopodium*, *Fagopyrum*, *Polygonum*, *Rumex*, *Cucumis*, *Brassica*, *Euphorbia*, *Oenothera*, *Vitis*, *Galium*, *Lycopersicon*, *Nicotiana*, *Solanum*, *Convolvulus*, *Phlox*, *Echium*, *Plantago*, *Achillea*, *Antennaria*, *Artemisia*, *Callistephus*, *Cichorium*, *Helianthus*, *Hieracium*, *Lactuca*, *Taraxacum*, *Tussilago*, *Avena*, *Calamagrostis*, *Elytrigia*, *Hordeum*, *Secale*, *Triticum*, *Zea*. The caterpillars live in the soil, gnawing the roots of foodplants (Matov et Kononenko 2012).

Conclusion

Thus, the fauna of Macrolepidoptera of Omsk Region now includes 1016 species. The number of Geometridae species in the fauna of Omsk Region is 266, Noctuidae – 376 species. The number of Lepidoptera species in Novosibirsk Region has been replenished with 7 species. The distribution of 14 species on the territory of the West Siberian Plain has been clarified.

Figures 16–23. Adult specimens of Lepidoptera: **16** – *Diacrisia metelkana*, Chebachye (CVIN); **17** – *Paragona cognata*, Karasuk (CVIN); **18** – *Catocala deducta*, Khorosheye (CVIN); **19** – *Acronicta menyanthidis*, Bezmyanny Ryam (CVIN); **20** – *Amphipyra pyramidea*, Novosibirsk (CVIN); **21** – *Egira conspicillaris*, Elita (CSKO); **22** – *Polia malchani*, Orlovka (CVIN); **23** – *Euxoa nigrofusca*, Shelkovichikha (CVIN).

Figures 24–31. Adult specimens of Lepidoptera in Nature: 24 – *Dasytoma salicella*, Ryazany (photo by S.A. Knyazev); 25 – *Stauropus fagi*, Bol'shiye Uki (photo by V.Yu. Teploukhov); 26 – *Limenitis camilla*, Firstovo (photo by V.Yu. Teploukhov); 27 – *Apatura ilia*, Firstovo (photo by V.Yu. Teploukhov); 28 – *Epirranthis diversata*, Ryazany (photo by S.A. Knyazev); 29 – *Pseudobaptria corydalaria*, Yakovlevka (photo by S.A. Knyazev); 30 – *Egira conspicillaris*, Elita (photo by S.A. Knyazev); 31 – *Simyra dentinosa*, Chernoluchye (photo by S.A. Knyazev).

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